

WAYS TO IMPROVE WRITING SKILLS

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Annotation: Writing is a technical skill that is used to communicate effectively through the written word. It includes grammar, vocabulary, spelling, sentence construction, structure, research and accuracy, clarity, and persuasiveness. Being able to write well is a form of effective communication, which employers seek in job candidates.

Key words: Grammar, Vocabulary, Spelling, Sentence construction, Structure, Research and accuracy, Clarity, Persuasiveness.

Аннотация: Письмо - это технический навык, который используется для эффективного общения с помощью письменного слова. Она включает в себя грамматику, словарный запас, орфографию, построение предложений, структуру, исследование, а также точность, ясность и убедительность. Умение хорошо писать - это форма эффективной коммуникации, которую работодатели ищут в кандидатах на работу.

Ключевые слова: Грамматика, словарный запас, орфография, построение предложения, структура, исследование и точность, Ясность, убедительность.

From sending emails to preparing presentations, writing is often a day-to-day task in many professions spanning diverse industries. Writing skills go beyond grammar and spelling. Accuracy, clarity, persuasiveness, and several other elements play a part in ensuring your writing is conveying the right message.

Writing is a technical skill that you use to communicate effectively through the written word. Though these may vary depending on what you're writing, there are several that transcend categories. Writing skills can more specifically include:

- Grammar
- Vocabulary
- Spelling
- Sentence construction
- Structure
- Research and accuracy
- Clarity
- Persuasiveness

Each of these components can influence the quality of writing.

Being able to write well is a form of effective communication, which many employers see as a crucial job skill. In fact, strong communication—spanning written, verbal, non-verbal, and visual—is among the nine common employability skills that employers seek in job candidates.

Regardless of your role, with good writing skills, you can clearly transcribe your thoughts into meaningful messages, enabling you to share your ideas, build relationships, and strengthen your professional image.

Writing, like any other skill, is something we can get better at with time and practice. Here are some strategies for developing your own written communication:

1. Review grammar and spelling basics.

Grammar and spelling form the foundation of good writing. Writing with proper grammar and spelling communicates your professionalism and attention to detail to your reader. It also makes your writing easier to understand.

Plus, knowing when and how to use less-common punctuation, like colons, semicolons, and em-dashes, can unlock new ways to structure sentences and elevate your writing.

If you're looking to strengthen your grammar and spelling, start by consulting a writing manual. *The Elements of Style* by William Strunk and E.B. White has long been considered a staple for writers. You can find similar resources at your local library, bookstore, or online.

Read what you want to write.

Knowing what a finished piece of writing can look like can guide your own. If you're trying to write a humorous short story, read humorous short stories. Writing a book review? Find a few and take note of how they're structured. Pay attention to what makes them good and what you want to emulate (without plagiarizing, of course). If you're working on a school assignment, you can ask your instructor for examples of successful pieces from past students.

Make reading a part of your everyday life to improve your writing. Try reading the news in the morning or picking up a book before you head to bed. If you haven't been a big reader in the past, start with topics you're interested in, or ask friends and family for recommendations. You'll gradually begin to understand what subjects, genres, and authors you enjoy.

3. Proofread.

While it's tempting to submit work as soon as you're done with it, build in some time to revisit what you've written to catch errors big and small. Here are a few proofreading tips to keep in mind:

- **Set your work aside before you edit.** Try to step away from your writing for a day or more so you can come back to it with fresh, more objective eyes. Crunched for time? Even allotting 20 minutes between writing and proofreading can allow you to approach your work with renewed energy.
- **Start with easy fixes, then progress to bigger changes.** Starting with easier changes can get you in the rhythm for proofreading, allow you to read through your work once more, and clear distractions so you can focus on bigger edits. Read through your work to catch misspellings, inconsistencies, and grammar errors. Then address the larger problems with structure or awkward transitions.
- **If you could say something in fewer words, do so.** Being unnecessarily wordy can cloud your message and confuse the reader. Pare down phrases that are redundant, repetitive, or obvious.
- **Read out loud.** Reading out loud can help you find awkward phrases and areas where your writing doesn't flow well.

Whether you're writing emails or essays, asking for feedback is a great way to see how somebody besides yourself will interpret your text. Have an idea of what you'd like your proofreader to focus on—the structure, conclusion, the persuasiveness of an argument, or otherwise.

Approach a trusted friend, family member, coworker, or instructor. If you're a student, your school might also have a writing resource center you can reach out to.

You might also consider forming a writing group or joining a writing class. Find writing courses online, at your local community college, or at independent writing workshops in your city.

5. Think about structure.

Grammar and spelling keep your writing consistent and legible, but structure ensures the big ideas get across to the reader.

In many cases, forming an **outline** will help solidify structure. An outline can clarify what you're hoping to convey in each section, enable you to visualize the flow of your piece, and surface parts that require more research or thought.

Structure might look different depending on what you're writing. An essay typically has an introduction, body paragraphs, and a conclusion. A fiction piece might follow the six-stage plot structure: exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, resolution, and denouement. Choose what's best for your purposes.

Write.

Like many skills, one of the best ways to improve your writing is to practice. Here are a few ways you can get started:

- Start a journal or a blog.
- Join a class or writing workshop.
- Practice free writing.
- Write letters to friends or family.
- Put together an opinion piece for your local newspaper or publication you like.

7. Know some common fixes.

Even if a text is grammatically correct, you may be able to make it more dynamic and interesting with some polish. Here are some common ways you can sharpen your writing:

- Choose strong verbs (for example, "sprinted," "dashed," or "bolted" instead of "ran").
- Avoid passive voice.
- Vary sentence length.
- Cut unnecessary words.
- Replace clichés with original phrasing.

our writing skills will shine throughout the job search process, whether or not you intend to show them off. This is because job applications are largely written materials, including your cover letter, resume, and email communications. Use these opportunities to demonstrate your writing skills to prospective employers by submitting clear, accurate, and engaging materials. Additionally, if you have specialized expertise, such as experience with legal writing, medical writing, technical writing, or scientific writing, you can note that in a resume skills section and further detail that experience within your cover letter or during your interviews.

References:

1. <https://www.coursera.org/articles/writing-skills>;
2. "IELTS Information_for_Candidates_booklet" (PDF). Archived from the original (PDF) on 16 February 2011. Retrieved 26 February 2011.
3. "Facts & figures". englishuk.com. Retrieved 29 March 2022.
4. "IELTS | Researchers - History of IELTS". Archived from the original on 11 July 2015. Retrieved 8 July 2015. Accessed 08 July 2015

5. Jump up

"What is IELTS?". www.ielts.org. Retrieved 8 July 2015.

6. "Which IELTS test should I take?". 17 July 2019. Retrieved 18 August 2019.

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